

Optimizing robot cycle time in complex tasks with multiple configurations at the working points

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Abstract—Many industrial robotic tasks can be performed with multiple robot configurations at the working points (e.g., handling, assembly, soldering, deburring). In this paper, the Travelling salesman Problem (TSP) is exploited and enhanced to find the optimal cycle time of such complex tasks. Results show that cycle time can be optimized in such cases with very low computational time.

Index Terms—Industrial robots, cycle time, TSP, productivity

I. INTRODUCTION

In the most common industrial applications (e.g., assembly of parts, welding [1]) the cycle time is due to two components: active time, i.e., the time required to perform an active action, like the insertion of a component inside a slot; movement time, i.e., the time required to move from one position to another. While the former is generally fixed, the latter can be reduced via optimization processes. Such processes may rely on trajectory optimizations [2], but in many cases, it is also possible to reduce cycle time by varying the order of the tasks [3]. In fact, different task orders result in different movement times in moving between the working positions, thus changing cycle time.

To achieve task order optimization, the Travelling Salesman Problem (TSP) can be used [4]: in this problem, a salesman (i.e., the robot) must visit a set of cities (i.e., the working positions) by visiting each city once. The target is to minimize a cost function (e.g., energy, time).

In this paper, the TSP is enhanced to force the movement between points and to include clusters of cities (e.g., tasks to be performed with the same end effector) and multiple configurations at the same working position. An example will be provided to show the capabilities of this version of the TSP.

II. THE TRAVELLING SALESMAN PROBLEM

The TSP aims to find the fastest path ("tour") that passes through every point P once. The tour must be closed, thus the starting position is the only one that has to be visited two times. To solve the TSP, two matrices must be defined:

- X ($n \times n$), which contains all the possible connections between points. Its element x_{ij} represent the connection between P_i to P_j , are integers, and are equal to 1 if x_{ij} is included in the tour, 0 otherwise;

- C ($n \times n$), which contains all the costs of moving between points. Its element c_{ij} is the cost of the movement between P_i to P_j and may represent time, energy, or any other cost involved in the process.

The TSP finds X that solves the function:

$$\min \left(\sum_{i=1}^n \sum_{j \neq i, j=1}^n c_{ij} x_{ij} \right) \quad (1)$$

A. Standard algorithm constraints

To close the tour, the number of connections must equal the number of points. This constraint can be expressed as:

$$\sum_{i=1}^n \sum_{j \neq i, j=1}^n x_{ij} = n \quad (2)$$

Also, to describe the fact that each position has to be visited once, other conditions have to be stated:

$$\sum_{j \neq i, j=1}^n x_{ji} = 1 \quad , \quad \sum_{j \neq i, j=1}^n x_{ij} = 1 \quad (3)$$

Eq. 3 indicates that, for each point P_i , the number of the entering connections must be equal to 1 (to the left) and, in the same way, the number of exiting connections must be equal to 1 (to the right). At first, these constraints can lead to multiple closed paths ("subtours"). As a result, additional constraints must be added iteratively to remove subtours.

III. ENHANCING TSP CAPABILITIES

From now on, the paper shows some examples of how TSP algorithm can be tweaked to cope with additional constraints that may be imposed by the task.

A. Forcing (or avoiding) connections

Some applications (e.g., spraying) require the robot to move from P_i to P_j . As a result, one among x_{ij} and x_{ji} must be chosen in the solution, regardless of the cost of the connection. Such a constrain can be imposed as:

$$x_{ij} + x_{ji} = 1 \quad (4)$$

since the traveling direction is unknown a priori. In the same way, it is possible to constrain a connection not to be

performed. In this case, eq. 4 can be rearranged to fit the need in a very simple way:

$$x_{ij} + x_{ji} = 0 \quad (5)$$

B. Clustering of points

Some applications (e.g., assembly) require to perform different tasks with different end-effectors. As a result, it is convenient for the TSP solution to pass through all the points sharing the same end-effector before moving to another group. Hence, the points can be divided into clusters. For each cluster S , containing n_s positions, the TSP will define a non-closed subtour containing only the points of the cluster. This constraint can be defined as:

$$\sum_{i \neq j, i \in S, j \in S} x_{ij} = n_s - 1 \quad (6)$$

since the last connection that would close the tour has to be removed to connect the cluster with the other clusters.

Let's introduce set $R \subset X$ as a set that includes all the connections between the points of different clusters and n_c as the number of clusters. If $n_c > 1$, all the clusters have to be connected by a number of arches equal to the number of clusters (eq. 7). Also, each cluster has to connect at most once with any other cluster, only if $n_c > 2$ (eq. 8, where S_1 and S_2 are two generic clusters). This constraint does not apply to $n_c = 2$ because in this case the two clusters must be connected by two arches to obtain a closed path.

$$\sum_{i \neq j, i \in R, j \in R} x_{ij} = n_c \quad (7)$$

$$\sum_{i \in S_1, j \in S_2} x_{ij} = 1 \quad \text{if } n_c > 2 \quad (8)$$

C. Multiple configurations at working points

The concept of clusters can be adopted to include m configurations at working points, where all the configurations of P_i form a cluster. Each configuration is a point of the TSP. TSP cannot exclude points from the solution, thus additional constraints must be imposed. The proposed method (Fig. 1) consists of:

- 1) For each k configuration $P_{i,k}$, a copy is created $P_{i,k}^*$;
- 2) Within the cluster, $P_{i,k}$ is connected only to its copy ($P_{i,j}^*$, yellow lines) and to the copy of the following configuration ($P_{i,j+1}^*$, blue lines);
- 3) The number of blue lines must equal to m , while the number of yellow lines must equal $m - 1$. In total, each cluster contains $2m - 1$ connections.

As a result, matrix X greatly increases in size, but the TSP solution can be used in a complex application.

IV. EXPERIMENTAL RESULTS AND CONCLUSIONS

This version of the TSP is used in an example of a real case application, in which an Omron Viper s650 is used to capture some photos on the sides of a pyramid trunk. The camera sensor is rectangular; thus, the photo can be taken by rotating

Fig. 1: Example of connections within and between clusters. Each cluster comprises the configurations of a working point, together with the copies.

Fig. 2: Optimized robot movement for the case study (a) and order defined by the operator (b).

the camera axis by about 180° . To increase the complexity of the problem, both flip/no-flip configurations are considered.

The order provided by the TSP is compared to the order chosen by a human operator. The final movements are very similar, but the cycle time is very different: while the optimal movement (Fig. 2a) takes 2.92 s, the movement of the operator (Fig. 2b) takes 3.18 s, with a reduction of nearly 9%. The TSP solution is obtained with a computational time of 1.08 s on a mid-range Windows 10 laptop.

In conclusion, the TSP can be adapted to complex tasks to obtain a significant reduction in the overall movement time. The amount of time reduction may vary according to the complexity of the application, nonetheless, computational time is very low in any case [5], [6].

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